

***Bildung* as a Key to *Eudaimonia*: Aristotelian Foundations of Wilhelm von Humboldt's Educational Ideal**

Sabrina Bacher

Introduction

The recent revival of virtue ethics (e.g., Annas, 1993; Anscombe, 1959; Foot, 1978; MacIntyre 1981; Stocker, 1976; Zagzebski, 1997) has not only brought the idea of moral virtue, but also the Aristotelian interpretation of *eudaimonia* (εὐδαιμονία; approximately “flourishing,” “well-being,” “happiness”) as the ideal of a good human life back into philosophical discussion. *Eudaimonia* has also reemerged in the field of philosophy of education, as several contemporary philosophers (e.g., Brighouse, 2008; de Ruyter, 2004; Foucault, Defert, and Ewald, 2007; White, 2011) have underscored the importance of human flourishing as one of the chief goals of education. The connection between education and happiness is not limited to philosophy of education, but also investigated in empirical studies (e.g., Chen, 2012; Ruiu and Ruiu, 2019; Sung, 2016), considered with respect to curriculum design (e.g., MacConville and Rae, 2012; Morris, 2013; Sherab, Maxwell and Cooksey, 2014), and in teacher education programs (e.g., O'Brien, 2010). Furthermore, UNESCO draws and promotes the same parallel (e.g., Bacha, 2007; Faure, 1972; Marujo and Casais, 2001), particularly with regard to the interrelation between education and the third Sustainable Development Goal (SDG 3), Good Health and Well-being (UN General Assembly, 2015; UNESCO, 2021).

In the late 18th and early 19th century, German philosophers (e.g., Fichte, 1800/1962; Humboldt, 1793/2000; Kant, 1803; Schleiermacher, 1820-21/2008) opened an impassioned debate on the concept of *Bildung* and redefined it as a life-long inner formation of human beings as individuals. Wilhelm von Humboldt (1767-1835) is considered the leading figure among them. As a philosopher, linguist, diplomat, functionary, and one of the chief initiators of the University of Berlin (today Humboldt University of Berlin), he made a substantial contribution to the theory and practice of *Bildung*, which is still highly relevant today (Biesta, 2002; Reble, 2004). His encompassing conception not only contains a fundamental theoretical discourse but also elaborates on the conditions that are necessary for the implementation of *Bildung*. In this context, Humboldt (1792/1854) also addresses the imperilment of *Bildung* through external factors. On a practical level, his reform of the Prussian school system, in which he attempted to establish an organizational and administrative framework for the realization of his ideas, has had a lasting effect on education systems within and also outside the German-speaking world (cf. Berghahn, 2022; Shaw and Lenartowicz, 2016).

This paper explores the link between *eudaimonia* and Humboldt's concept of *Bildung*. I argue that *Bildung* in the Humboldtian way of interpretation strives for *eudaimonia* as its underlying goal and can be seen as a pathway towards *eudaimonia*. Throughout the paper, I justify this assertion

by referring to both Humboldt’s biography and his philosophical work. First, I examine his background and the historical context of his time, which incited him to delve into Greek philosophy, as well as to embrace the general mindset and way of living of the ancient Greeks. Next, I elucidate how this dedication influenced the foundations of his concept of *Bildung* and his reasoning by collating manuscripts from both Humboldt and Aristotle regarding the inner formation of individuals. Through a comparison of their argumentation, I intend to clarify to what extent they match. Finally, I portray how Humboldt developed his thoughts further by indicating conditions that are necessary for *Bildung*, and in consequence, *eudaimonia*, to unfold. The article concludes with a systemized outline of Humboldt’s theory of *Bildung* with *eudaimonia* as its ultimate goal.

1. Background Information on Humboldt’s Concept of Bildung

While the philosophical discussion on Humboldt and his concept of *Bildung* has remained prevalent in the German-speaking world (e.g., Adorno, 1959; Benner, 2003; Berghahn, 2022; Gadamer, 1960/2010; Gruber, 1999; Horkheimer, 1953; Liessmann, 2006; Menze, 1975; Meyer, 2011; Nida-Rümelin, 2013; Prüwer, 2009), the international arena has paid less attention to him and his ideas. This becomes apparent by comparing the frequency of the occurrence of “Wilhelm von Humboldt” respectively with his anglicized name “William von Humboldt” in a corpus of books in both German and English sources printed between his lifetime and today. The yearly count found in those texts shows a significant difference, as illustrated in the figure below (Google Books Ngram Viewer, 2022).

Fig. 1. Frequency of occurrence of “Wilhelm von Humboldt” in a corpus of books in both German and English

The results are similar for other languages. Not only has Humboldt himself received less consideration outside of the German-speaking world, but so has his concept of *Bildung*. Therefore, I provide additional background information on Humboldt and his idea of *Bildung*.

Bildung has been lost in translation in the English language. There is no specific word to accurately represent the concept of *Bildung* in English. Even though *Bildung* is frequently translated as ‘education,’ the conceptional range of *Bildung* is narrower and more specific than that of ‘education,’ which traces back to the Latin etymon ‘educatio’ (Hörner, Drinck and Jobst, 2010, pp. 11-12). Contrary to ‘education,’ notions such as ‘self-cultivation,’ ‘self-formation,’ or ‘fulfillment of one’s potential’ certainly present a higher degree of conceptional similarity with

Bildung than does ‘education.’ Nevertheless, although not always explicitly worded, the demand for a more *Bildung*-centered idea of education has been vital among renowned philosophers of education in the English speaking world as well (e.g., Dewey, 1902; Nussbaum, 2016; Rawls, 1971; Whitehead, 1929/1976).

Vice versa, German does not have a term precisely equivalent to ‘education,’ so ‘education’ cannot be accurately translated into German. Instead, the German language offers a semantic distinction between different forms of education: *Erziehung* (approximately “upbringing”), *Ausbildung* (approximately “vocational-training”), and, as aforementioned, *Bildung*. In contrast to *Erziehung* and *Ausbildung*, *Bildung* does not necessarily refer to an interrelation between two or more people where—in most cases—one passes on skills, knowledge, or values to the other(s). According to Humboldt (1809/2017), *Bildung* rather emphasizes the personal fulfillment of one’s unique potential as a life-long process (p. 112). Nevertheless, individuals can inspire others to strike the path towards *Bildung* or ensure the conditions that are necessary for it to unfold (Humboldt, 1792/1854, p. 11 ff.). Furthermore, the three forms of education aim at divergent objectives. *Erziehung* and *Ausbildung* in general aspire to the socialization of young people, whereas *Bildung* pursues a different goal, which is, as I argue in this article, *eudaimonia* of the individual and, in consequence, of humankind in its entirety.

While *Bildung* is one of the main topics in almost all of Humboldt’s writings, he never systematized his ideas into a theory and only wrote a few fragments exclusively on *Bildung* (Lauer, 2017, p. 252). This is because for Humboldt, writing was rather a way to clarify and deepen his thoughts than to address a broad audience (Reble, 2004, p. 193). Even the title of his short manuscript “Theory of *Bildung*” (Humboldt, 1793/2000) (original title: “*Theorie der Bildung der Menschen*,” 1793/1960) is misleading, as it only contains a fraction of his thoughts on *Bildung*. Instead, Humboldt’s ideas that constitute his concept of *Bildung* are integrated into a variety of his texts. For example, his philosophical treatise *The Sphere and Limits of Government (The Limits of State Action)* (Humboldt, 1792/1854) (original title: *Ideen zu einem Versuch die Grenzen der Wirksamkeit des Staats zu bestimmen*, 1792/1851) contains essential passages that reveal parts of the foundation of his concept of *Bildung*. In addition, several of his thoughts and ideas were considered as too liberal and radical during his lifetime, and thus these writings were published only after his death (Lauer, 2017, p. 256). Therefore, his theory of *Bildung* can only be fully reconstructed from his complete writings in combination with his biography and the historical context of his time.

2. Influential Circumstances in Humboldt’s Idea of Bildung

Humboldt’s philosophical œuvre is mirrored by his life. Hence, to understand his train of thought, it is fundamental to gain an insight in some of the circumstances of his lifetime, as they *vigorously influenced* his ideas on *Bildung*. In the following, I argue that not only his writings but also his biography displays the intertwining between *Bildung* and *eudaimonia*. Humboldt was born in 1767 into a wealthy aristocratic family and spent most of his childhood at the Humboldt family estate, the castle of Tegel near Berlin, which was then in Prussia. Wilhelm and his famous brother, Alexander, enjoyed a privileged but still afflicted childhood. Their father died unexpectedly when Wilhelm was eleven years old, while their mother was unaffectionate and neglected her children’s emotional wellbeing. Under these circumstances, Wilhelm withdrew into a world of books and

lost himself in Greek antiquity, which later became a fundamental pillar of his concept of *Bildung*, while Alexander devoted himself to the exploration of nature. Their mother's sole focus was to foster her sons' intellectual and moral perfection, so she sought to provide them with the best education available (Wulf, 2016, pp. 13-15). Both boys were educated by renowned private tutors, such as Joachim Heinrich Campe, Johann Jakob Engel, and Christian Wilhelm Dohm, who imparted a broad general knowledge in the educational tradition of the Enlightenment. Their curriculum included subjects like ancient Greek, Latin, math, botany, physics, geography, philosophy, theology, economy, technology, natural law, and drawing (Lauer, 2017, p. 238). Truth, knowledge, and tolerance were some of the core values. Nevertheless, their educators followed a mainstream pedagogical approach with neither an understanding of child development nor room for the joy of learning (Holl, 2016, pp. 15-16). Despite their broad general education, *eudaimonia* was certainly not the main goal of their upbringing. Nevertheless, in their adolescence Wilhelm and Alexander were occasionally able to escape from their family constraints in Tegel to get a taste of the Berlin air. Accompanied by their educators, they spent a significant amount of time in Berlin, where they were introduced to the highest intellectual circles, participated in reading groups, and visited philosophical salons. These experiences unveiled the social aspect of learning to them and provided room for both to flourish (Klencke and Schlesier, 2009, pp. 15-16), or in other words, these intellectual adventures inspired them to strive for further growth and *Bildung*. However, in their early adulthood their mother impeded the Humboldt brothers' academic freedom by determining the path of their university education. She expected her sons to follow a career as exalted civil servants, and, since they were financially dependent on her, they had no choice but to obey her wishes (Schaffstein 1952, p. 24). Therefore, Wilhelm had to begin his university studies in law in Frankfurt an der Oder, but changed to the University of Göttingen after one semester. Although he abandoned his studies in Göttingen after another three semesters without a degree, this chapter in his life was essential for his personal and intellectual progression.

Humboldt generated the main ideas for his concept of *Bildung* during his student days in Göttingen. Not only was the University of Göttingen an intellectual center of political science favored by aristocrats headed for government positions, but also a central location of *Neuhumanismus* (German New Humanism), a movement that deeply influenced and shaped Humboldt's idea of *Bildung* (Bruford, 1971, p. 235). *Neuhumanismus* emerged during the second part of the 18th century and arose in connection with the literary and artistic movement of *Sturm und Drang* (Storm and Stress) (Hauer 2000, p. 486). Initiated by some of the German educated elites (e.g., Johann Wolfgang von Goethe, Friedrich Schiller, Johann Gottfried Herder), the *Sturm und Drang* movement criticized the one-sided focus on reason and the devaluation of emotion which was predominant during the Age of Enlightenment. This fundamental change in thinking also impacted pedagogy. Instead of educating and moralizing people to become law-abiding citizens, *Neuhumanismus* promoted a holistic, inner development of human beings as individuals. Imagination, aesthetics, art, personal development, and individuation played an important role in this process. A second key element of *Neuhumanismus* was the establishment of harmony both within the individual and between the individual and the outside world. The world of the classic era was considered as a prototype for such an encompassing concept of self-formation. By studying and interpreting ancient Greek language and culture, humans were supposed to be driven towards self-formation, that is, the realization of their fullest potential (Reble, 2004, pp. 174-186). A return to the ideal of the ancient Greeks should support the individual's quest for identity, virtue, and flourishing.

Inspired by *Neuhumanismus*, Humboldt devoted a significant amount of time to the detailed reading of ancient philosophy. He idealized the ancient Greeks as models of a perfection of humankind because he thought they had created a holistic connection between nature and culture (Andrzejewski, 2011, p. 26). Furthermore, Humboldt (1792/1864) admired how the “*ancients* devoted their attention more exclusively to the harmonious development of the individual [...] [and] looked to virtue” (p. 7). In consequence, he formed a society for the development of virtue, a secret club dedicated to mutual moral improvement. There he met his future wife, Carolina von Dacheröden, who was highly sophisticated herself and further inspired his idea of *Bildung* (Sorkin, 1983, p. 57).

Beyond books and intellectual exchange, travelling and living abroad were additional ways for Humboldt to broaden his horizons and strive towards *Bildung*. In 1789, after his studies, he set forth on an educational journey to Paris, Southern Germany, and Switzerland, where he established intellectual connections with renowned scholars, explorers, and freethinkers. Over the years, he cultivated deep friendships with admired intellectuals, such as Goethe and Schiller. His varied experience led him to gradually reject the reason-based education of his youth in the tradition of the earlier years of Enlightenment and he began to question his anticipated career (Sorkin, 1983, p. 57). Nevertheless, after his journey, he joined the Prussian civil service as a law clerk to the Supreme Court of Berlin, but retired into private life after a few months because he found no satisfaction in his work and wanted to dedicate time to his writing. In 1802, he rejoined the Prussian civil service and became an envoy to the Vatican in Rome, which enabled him to delve even deeper into the history, culture, and mindset of classical Greece and Rome.

Apart from his own biography, the changing ideas during his lifetime, such as the social and political upheaval around the turn of the century, also influenced Humboldt’s conception of *Bildung*. After the defeat of Prussia by Napoleon, the state collapsed in 1806 and had to reorganize itself. The estate-based society turned into a civil society, and the feudal state into an administrative state. The Prussian Reform Movement brought constitutional, administrative, social, and economic reforms. These changes also affected the education system. In 1809, Humboldt was asked to return to Prussia to lead the directorate of education. In this position, he was one of the designers of the educational reforms and tried to revamp the Prussian educational system according to his concept of *Bildung* (Sorkin, 1983, pp. 55-56).

Humboldt’s *The Königsberg and the Lithuanian School Plan (Der Königsberger und der Litauische Schulplan, 1809/2022)* provides an overview of how he intended to implement his ideas. He was an advocator for cost-free schools that provide a broad general education for everyone, so each individual can find and develop his or her potential regardless of social status and prospective career. He also promoted a three-tier education system in which each level pursues a different goal. Based on the pedagogical ideas and teaching methods of Pestalozzi, elementary schools build the foundation for the subsequent levels of education. Thus, young school children should mainly acquire and practice skills, such as writing, reading, and calculating, that are prerequisites for learning. These skills should be integrated into their daily life with the help of subsidiary subjects. At the secondary level, Humboldt envisioned a comprehensive school for all adolescents, who should acquire knowledge and skills that are essential for scientific insight and artistry. They should immerse themselves into a variety of subjects, such as classical languages,

history, geography, natural sciences, math, and physics. This level aims at enhancing the maturity of young people, who should eventually become autonomous learners, emancipate themselves from their teachers, and continue their further education with intrinsic motivation. What follows is the tertiary level. At university, students should be guided and supported in their independent research and gain a holistic understanding of science, with a focus on philosophy as the mother of all sciences. Therefore, Humboldt also envisioned a general education instead of occupational training at the tertiary level. Moreover, he advocated for academic freedom and a unity of research and teaching.

Due to his opposition to state restrictions and a conflict with the state chancellor of Prussia, he resigned from state service after one year but remained chairman of the founding committee of the University of Berlin. Even though Humboldt's educational policy concept did not gain general acceptance and he could only achieve a partial success in the first place, his ideas paved the way for fundamental educational reforms. In the following years, Humboldt served as a representative of the Prussian government to the Congress of Vienna and the Aachen Congress. In 1819, he was appointed Minister of Estates in the Prussian government, but resigned after a few months due to internal conflicts (UNESCO, 1993). Humboldt spent the rest of his life with personal, continuing self-formation and scientific correspondence with scholars from various parts of the world (Meyer, 1991, p. 201).

Humboldt's background reveals that he was drawn towards *Bildung*, which resulted in a conflict between his character and parts of his formal education during his childhood (Sorkin, 1983, pp. 55-56). Regarding the relationship between *Bildung* and *eudaimonia*, I would like to particularly highlight his devotion to the ancient Greeks since his childhood, his dedication to *Neuhumanismus* since his youth, and his overall intrinsically motivated thirst for *Bildung* that ran like a golden thread throughout his entire life. In essence, Humboldt did not only preach *Bildung*, but also lived it, as it enabled him in his quest for personal fulfillment, and hence guided him towards *eudaimonia*.

This historical and biographical contextualization builds the foundation for understanding Humboldt's thoughts on *Bildung*. It is important to note that his ideas do not solely arise from his written work but are fundamentally intertwined with his background. Since his texts are at times fragmented, background knowledge is essential to reconcile contradictions and fill the gaps. Consequently, this biographical foundation provides the basis for reconstructing his train of thought as related to *Bildung*. With this in mind, we can examine the interrelation between the Humboldtian concept of *Bildung* and the Aristotelian interpretation of *eudaimonia*.

3. Aristotelian Roots in Humboldt's Notion of Bildung

In the previous section I contextualized Humboldt's concept of *Bildung* through the lens of history, so that our topic can be understood in all its complexity and depth. With reference to Humboldt's biography and the context of his lifetime, I showed that Greek antiquity served as a role model for him because he saw the original character of humanity best represented by the ancient Greeks. A closer look into the topic shows that Humboldt's anthropological convictions also provide the ethical foundation for his concept of *Bildung*. The essence of this concept coincides substantially with Greek philosophy, more specifically with Aristotelean ethics. In the following, I explore the

extent to which Humboldt's and Aristotle's conceptions of the nature of human beings and the fulfilling of their potential coincide by focusing on the similarities and differences in their lines of argument, and by comparing and contrasting several of Humboldt's and Aristotle's ideas.

3.1. *Eudaimonia* as the Primary Goal of Existence

The central concept in Aristotle's ethics is *eudaimonia* (εὐδαιμονία; approximately "flourishing," "well-being," "happiness"). Even though most modern languages do not offer a term that accurately represents its meaning, in English *eudaimonia* is frequently translated as happiness. This can be misleading, because *eudaimonia* does not represent a positive feeling but rather a distinctive form of happiness or well-being which refers to a state of flourishing (Besser-Jones, 2016, p. 187). In his *Nicomachean Ethics* Aristotle (ca. 350 B.C.E./1894) clarifies his specific understanding of *eudaimonia*. He criticizes the fact that some people interpret it as "pleasure" or "honor," while others understand it with regard to their current state, such that, for instance, the sick generally relate it to "health" and the poor to "wealth." However, if we live a life dedicated to pleasure (*bios apolaustikos*) or wealth (*bios chrêmatistês*), we turn into slaves of our needs or become fully dependent on others. Therefore, as Aristotle points out, such interpretations are superficial. Nevertheless, "apart from these many goods there is another which is self-subsistent and causes the goodness of all these as well" (1.4). In other words, according to Aristotle, *eudaimonia* is the *telos teleiôtaton* or ultimate goal of life. In his own words, "[v]erballly there is very general agreement; for both the general run of men and people of superior refinement say that it is [...] [*eudaimonia*], and identify living well and doing well with being happy" (1.4). In short, the essential purpose in life for any being is *eudaimonia*, which benefits both individuals and society alike.

The sentence fragment "happiness for which man is plainly destined" (Humboldt, 1792/1851, p. 27) is a rare example in which Humboldt explicitly refers to happiness as the primary goal of human life. Humboldt's remarks on happiness are neither as clear and detailed as Aristotle's, nor does he devote entire passages to the portrayal of a concept such as *eudaimonia*. In the original German version of *The Sphere and Limits of Government (The Limits of State Action)* (Humboldt, 1792/1854), *Ideen zu einem Versuch, die Grâenzen der Wirksamkeit des Staats zu bestimmen* (Humboldt, 1792/1851), he uses both *Glück* and *Glückseligkeit* to refer to happiness without a terminological distinction. Yet if we read between the lines, we notice an implicit differentiation of the divergent interpretations in the contextual sphere. In some passages Humboldt refers to happiness in a superficial way with an interpretation in the form of pleasure or wealth (e.g., pp. 42, 55, 71), which he condemns, just like Aristotle. In other passages he relates to happiness in a deeper sense (e.g., pp. 59, 103, 121), which resembles *eudaimonia*. Hence, Aristotle's idea of *eudaimonia* as the autotelic main purpose of life implicitly resonates to a great extent in Humboldt's argumentation. This becomes apparent if we take a closer look at both philosophers' train of thought and further concepts they use.

3.2. The Actualization of one's Potential

After defining *eudaimonia* as the essential purpose of life, Aristotle (ca. 350 B.C.E./1894) raises the question of how we can reach *eudaimonia*. He argues that all living beings can attain *eudaimonia* through the fulfillment of their *ergon* (ἐργον; approximately "function"), which is

essential to their cause by nature. In his own words, “for all things that have a function [...], the good and the 'well' is thought to reside in the function” (1.4). In short, performing one’s specific function well leads toward *eudaimonia*. The central idea of Aristotle’s argument is that the actualization of one’s potential is the key to *eudaimonia*. Throughout his works *Physics* (ca. 350 B.C.E./1970), *Metaphysics* (ca. 350 B.C.E./1999), *Nicomachean Ethics* (ca. 350 B.C.E./1894), *Rhetoric* (ca. 350 B.C.E./1924), and *De Anima* (ca. 350 B.C.E./2016), he analyzes the connected principles of potentiality and actuality with regard to causality, motion, physiology, and ethics. Aristotle assumes that all living beings carry the germ of their perfect form within, which unfolds naturally in the course of their development. He uses the term *dunamis* (δύναμις) to refer to “potentiality,” which is the actual nature of a thing or being and unfolds due to its innate tendency of change. In contrast to ‘potentiality,’ ‘actuality’ refers to the realization of that potential. In this context, Aristotle introduces the neologisms *energeia* (ἐνέργεια) and *entelecheia* (ἐντελέχεια) to refer to actuality. Most translators consider the two terms as synonyms (e.g., Bradshaw, 2004, p. 13), and, according to Aristotle (ca. 350 B.C.E./1999, 1047a30), their meanings were intended to converge. Yet there is an ambiguity in their usage. For example, in some places *energeia* may refer to an “actualization” of one’s physical, intellectual, or mental capacities, while elsewhere, *energeia* may allude to “activity” (Chen, 1956, 56-65), which may be interpreted as the performance of specific activities that pursue the goal of *eudaimonia*. Essentially, both concepts refer to a natural development, inherent in all living beings, towards their ideal form. Aristotle intends to explain this development according to the principle of cause and effect (Werner, 2021, 29).

In accordance with Aristotle, Humboldt (1792/1854) also claims that all beings, by nature, strive towards flourishing, and, therefore, have a desire to fulfill their potential. For example, “in the vegetable world, the simple and less graceful form of the fruit seems to prefigure the more perfect bloom and symmetry of the flower which it precedes, and which it is destined gradually to unfold” (p. 14-15). He was inspired by the idea of an instinct for self-formation, a so-called *nisus formativus* (approximately “formative drive”), presented by his teacher Johann Friedrich Blumenbach, who believed that everything in nature strives to evolve according to its unique given nature, so diversity can flourish (Lauer, 2017, 240, 252). According to Humboldt (1792/1854), the fulfillment of one’s potential can only be initiated extrinsically to a minor degree, as it mainly derives intrinsically. He claims that “whatever [each hu]man receives externally, is only as the grain of seed. It is [...] [their] own active energy alone that can convert the germ of the fairest growth, into a full and precious blessing for [...] [themselves]. It leads to beneficial issues only when it is full of vital power and essentially individual” (p. 15).

In this regard, Humboldt elaborates on a conception similar to Aristotle’s idea of potentiality and actuality. He uses the German terms *Kraft* (approximately “force,” “strength,” “power”), *Energie* (approximately “energy”), *Trieb* (approximately “urge,” “instinct”), and *Sehnsucht* (approximately “desire”) to refer to actuality, but uses them ambiguously and inconsistently (Surböck, 2012). In general, these terms can be interpreted as describing innate life forces or vital powers that are interconnected and that differ from person to person. *Kraft*, *Energie*, *Trieb*, and *Sehnsucht* enable humans to fulfill their specific potential, or, in Humboldt’s (1792/1854) words, they capacitate individuals to “cultivate [...] the physical, intellectual, and moral faculties” (p. 8). He further argues that “those energies [...] are the source of every active virtue, and the indispensable condition of any higher and more various culture” (p. 8). Thus, they are the driving

forces of *Bildung*. He even refers to *Energie* as the most important human virtue, or, in his own words, “[e]nergy appears to me to be the first and chiefest of human virtues. Whatever exalts our energy is of greater worth than aught that merely puts materials into our hands for its exercise” (p. 100). Humboldt’s concept of *Bildung* aims at the free development of humans as individuals, and he emphasizes that their vital powers and capacities differ from person to person. Aristotle’s ethics, on the other hand, aims at the realization of a general human nature that is similar for all human beings (Werner, 2021, p. 31). Therefore, their ideas on the actualization of one’s potential differ insofar as Humboldt interprets self-realization in the spirit of individuality, which plays a minor role in Aristotle’s argument.

3.3. The Function of *Logos* or the Rational Principle

Prima facie, it seems as if Aristotle’s and Humboldt’s views with reference to the function of human beings share important aspects. According to Aristotle (ca. 350 B.C.E./1894), the distinctive feature of human beings as opposed to other living beings is *logos* (λόγος; approximately “rational principle”). Just like several other central Aristotelian terms, *logos* is not only difficult to interpret but also challenging to translate. There are thorough philosophical surveys on *logos* (e.g., Anton, 2016; Aygün, 2017) that illustrate the complexity of Aristotle’s diction. In Aristotle’s (ca. 350 B.C.E./1894) own words, “[t]here remains [...] an active life of the element that has a rational principle” (1.7.). The rational principle differentiates humans from other species. Aristotle further argues that the *ergon* of humans is to fulfill the characteristic human *energeia* (here: “activity”) guided by *logos*, or in other words, the “function of man is an activity of soul which follows or implies a rational principle” (1.7). Hence, the function of human beings is to fulfill their potential by performing characteristic human activities guided by their rational principle.

In this context, Humboldt (1792/1854) explicitly refers to Aristotle’s connection between *logos* and *eudaimonia* by drawing a “conclusion with an illustrative passage from Aristotle’s Ethics:— ‘For that which peculiarly belongs to each by nature, is best and most pleasant to every one; and consequently, to man, the life according to intellect (is most pleasant), if intellect especially constitutes Man. This life therefore is the most happy’” (p. 9). Similar to Aristotle, Humboldt also regards the rational principle as an essential, characteristic feature of human beings and thinks that the development of intellectual abilities leads towards human perfection. In his own words, “[t]he true end of [each hu]man, or that which is prescribed by the eternal and immutable dictates of reason, and not suggested by vague and transient desires” (p. 11), is the actualization of their potential. However, in other passages, Humboldt emphasizes that reason is not the only component in the process of self-fulfillment. This also becomes apparent with regard to his biography. Inspired by *Neuhumanismus*, Humboldt claims that “in order to preserve society’s warmth and strength without which it will bear no inner fruit, it becomes just as necessary to keep the imagination and sentiment within a tight circle as it is to lead reason toward a broader sphere” (p. 9). Thus, he views self-realization holistically as a harmonious development of the human mind, spirit, and body, guided by reason (p. 11), imagination, and emotion.

3.4. The Role of *Arete* or Virtue

With respect to the relationship between virtue and human flourishing, Humboldt's and Aristotle's ideas also bear several common elements. Aristotle (ca. 350 B.C.E./1894) claims that *arete* (*ἀρετή*; approximately "virtue," "excellence") is autotelic as well as telic, because virtues are both self-sufficient and a means towards *eudaimonia*. In his words, "honour, pleasure, reason, and every virtue we choose indeed for themselves [...], but we choose them also for the sake of happiness, judging that by means of them we shall be happy" (1.7). On the one hand, virtues are autotelic because they derive meaning and purpose from within. Aristotle claims that a virtuous life is a happy life, which can be lived in two ways: a life of moral and political virtues (*bios politikos*) or a life of scientific and philosophical virtues (*bios theôrêtikos*) (Höffe 2013, 58). On the other hand, virtues are telic because they pursue a specific goal, which is *eudaimonia*. Virtues are qualities that enable humans to fulfill their *ergon*. In other words, they capacitate humans to perform their characteristic human activities guided by reason. Thus, humans can pursue *eudaimonia* by performing characteristic human activities, which are enabled by *arete* and guided by *logos* (Aristoteles, ca. 350 B.C.E./1894, 1.7). Inspired by Plato's four cardinal virtues (wisdom, courage, temperance, and justice), described in book IV of Plato's *Republic* (ca. 380 B.C.E./1935), Aristotle lists specific virtues and extends Plato's list by including other practical and intellectual virtues. For example, in *Rhetoric* (ca. 350 B.C.E./1924), Aristotle claims that "[t]he forms of [v]irtue are justice, courage, temperance, magnificence, magnanimity, liberality, gentleness, prudence, [and] wisdom" (1.9). All these traits are virtuous because they are necessary for humans to live a life of well-being. In other passages of his works, Aristotle extends this list even further.

In accordance with Aristotle, Humboldt (1792/1854) also regards virtue both as self-sufficient and as a means towards flourishing. In conjunction with his glorification of the ancient Greeks, he asserts that the "ancients sought for happiness in virtue" (p. 9). According to Humboldt, virtue is a pivotal aspect of human nature. In this context, he claims that "[v]irtue harmonizes [...] sweetly and naturally with [each hu]man's original inclinations" (p. 91) and that virtues do "not depend on any particular form of being, nor are necessarily connected with any particular aspect of character" (p. 70). Instead, humans develop virtues naturally through *Bildung*, as the full development of one's potential, or the "harmony [...] of all the different features of [...] [each hu]man's character" (p. 70) enables individuals to find to their primordial nature. For example, "love, [...] social concord, [...] justice, [...] [and] self-sacrifice" (p. 90) are part of original human nature and enable humans to develop relationships, as "domestic and social life contribute so largely to human happiness, that it is far less necessary to look for new incentives to virtuous action, than simply to secure for those already implanted in the soul a more free and unhindered operation" (p. 90).

The quintessence of Aristotle's and Humboldt's common line of thought is that all beings, by nature, have a desire to flourish, or in other words, a desire for *eudaimonia*. They can approach *eudaimonia* by actualizing their specific potential. In this context, Humboldt emphasizes the benefits of individuality and diversity, which plays a minor role in Aristotle's reasoning. According to Aristotle, the distinctive feature that differentiates humans from other beings is *logos*, which should, therefore, guide the development of one's capacities. While Humboldt also views reason as a fundamental component in this process, his approach is more holistic, as besides reason he emphasizes imagination and emotion. Both philosophers agree on the role of virtue by claiming that virtue is both autotelic and telic. Thus, a virtuous life is a happy life, and, at the same time,

virtue enables humans to perform their function well, and, thus, aims at *eudaimonia*. Humboldt extends this idea further by exploring the practical implications of these ideas, which I will investigate in the next section.

4. *The Essential Conditions of Humboldt’s Ideal of Bildung*

After exploring the foundation of Humboldt’s educational ideal of *Bildung* and the connection between *Bildung* and *eudaimonia*, questions like the following may arise: If all beings have an urge for *Bildung*, why does the level of this desire vary? Why are some humans more successful in fulfilling their potential than others? Can we foster *Bildung*, and, if so, how? Humboldt (1792/1854) claims that *Bildung* is subject to two conditions: freedom and exposure to a variety of situations (p. 11-15).

Fig. 2: *The conditions for the practical implementation of Bildung*

These conditions are intertwined. In combination, they are both necessary and sufficient for the practical realization of *Bildung*.

According to Humboldt (1792/1854), freedom “is the grand and indispensable condition” (p. 11) for *Bildung* because it allows the human mind to strive for *Bildung* from within. To put it differently, if freedom is ensured, an intrinsically motivated thirst for *Bildung* unfolds naturally (Lauer, 2017, p. 256). Humboldt (1792/1854) argues that only individuals who are free from social, governmental, and economic constraints can realize their full potential, because freedom enables humans to emancipate themselves from authoritarian structures and empowers them to think and act critically, independently, and responsibly. Hence, they can develop into unconstrained individuals instead of obedient citizens (pp. 66 ff.). While freedom initially fosters the personal fulfillment of individuals, the self-realization of a sufficiently large number of people eventually evolves into the flourishing of humankind in its entirety. In his own words, among free humans “emulation naturally arises” (p. 69). The quote below illustrates how Humboldt develops this idea further:

Among [...] [humans] who are really free, every form of industry becomes more rapidly improved,—all the arts flourish more gracefully,—all sciences become more largely enriched and expanded. In such a community, too, domestic bonds become closer and sweeter; the parents are more eagerly devoted to the care of their children, and, in a higher state of welfare, are better able to follow out their desires with regard to them [...] and tutors better benefit themselves. (p. 69)

In a nutshell, Humboldt claims that freedom implies many beneficial effects for humankind, which are visible in a variety of spheres, such as economy, art, science, domestic life, welfare, and education. Accordingly, ensuring freedom leads to a good human life and lays the foundation for future generations to flourish.

Besides freedom, Humboldt's second fundamental condition for *Bildung* is exposure to a variety of situations, which can be divided into three subcategories: (1) educational content, (2) personal experience, and (3) social interaction. According to Humboldt, humans evolve and broaden their horizons by gaining a wide range of theoretical and practical knowledge in combination with a lively exchange of ideas. Hence, exposure to a variety of situations leads to growth and progress. *Bildung* is nourished by diverse intellectual stimulation and experience, such as a holistic general knowledge, travel, and human relationships (Løvlie and Standish, 2002, p. 318). By being exposed to a variety of situations, as Humboldt explains (1792/1854), humans develop a holistic and multi-perspective view of the world. Therefore, “[e]ven the most free and self-reliant [...] [individual] is thwarted and hindered in [...] [their] development by uniformity of position” (p. 11). Humboldt claims that humans are by nature versatile and, therefore, should avoid one-sidedness. Instead of concentrating on one subject, they should broaden their minds and develop their capacities and skills holistically.

Consequently, Humboldt (1809/2017) expects educational content to be rich in variety and advocates for a broad general education for everybody, regardless of their social background and anticipated career. In *The Königsberg and the Lithuanian School Plan* (1809/2022) he claims that “[g]eneral secondary education is devoted to the complete human being [...] in the principle functions of [...] [their] natural being” (para. 4). Thus, curricula must be holistic, so that individuals can find and fulfill their potential, as he explains in the following quote:

This complete education therefore has but one and the same foundation. For the minds of the commonest day laborer and the most highly educated person must be tuned to the same key in the first place, if the former is not to become crude on a level beneath human dignity, and the latter is not to become sentimental, chimerical, and eccentric, falling short of human potential. (para. 6)

Humboldt illustrates this further in a letter to the king of Prussia: “There are undeniably certain kinds of knowledge that must be of a general nature and, more importantly, a certain cultivation of the mind and character that nobody can afford to be without” (Humboldt, 1809, as cited in Günther, 1988, p. 132). Furthermore, Humboldt (1792/1854) argues that humans should “unite the separate faculties of [...] [their] nature” and endeavor to “increase and diversify [...] [their] powers [...] by harmoniously combining them, instead of looking for a mere variety of objects for their separate exercise” (p. 11). Thus, he envisions a world where humans can recognize and realize their individual full potential with the help of a broad general education before their job training. In the following quote, he describes how such an educational background not only fosters personal fulfillment, but also leads to positive effects on the professional sphere:

People obviously cannot be good craftworkers, merchants, soldiers or businessmen unless, regardless of their occupation, they are good, upstanding and—according to their condition—well-informed human beings and citizens. If this basis is laid

through schooling, vocational skills are easily acquired later on, and a person is always free to move from one occupation to another, as so often happens in life. (Humboldt, 1809, as cited in Günther, 1988, p. 132)

According to Humboldt, such a general education should be interdisciplinary, integrate intellectuality, sensuality, and imagination (Günther, 1988, p. 89), and animate individuals to fulfill their individual potential (Sorkin, 1983, p. 58).

Personal experience and social interaction between the individual and the environment are further essential ways to expose oneself to a variety of situations. A connection between the internal and external world stimulates the individual to reflect, strengthen, and further develop their character holistically (Løvlie and Standish, 2002). Humboldt is convinced that individuals can only understand themselves in relation to the world. Their experience and interaction with the world expands the boundaries of individual existence (Spranger, 1909, p. 424 ff.) and leads their self-awareness towards world citizenship and cosmopolitanism. Humboldt (1793/2000) describes the necessity of the interaction between the individual and the world in the following way:

At the convergence point of all particular kinds of activity is [the hu]man, who, in the absence of a purpose with a particular direction, wishes only to strengthen and heighten the powers of [...] [their] nature and secure value and permanence for [...] [their] being. However, because sheer power needs an object on which it may be exercised and pure form or idea needs a material in which, expressing itself, it can last, so too does [each hu]man need a world outside [...] [themselves]. (p. 58)

In this context, Humboldt, who also made essential contributions in the field of linguistics, emphasizes the important role of language as a means by which individuals can fulfill their individual potential (Seidel, 1962, p. 207). It is language that enables social interaction and integrates humans into a socio-cultural environment. Human thoughts, feelings, and lives are shaped by language (Humboldt, 1822/1905, p. 432). Language allows a connection between the individual and the outside world, which is necessary to understand the world holistically (Burger, 2013, p. 165). Speaking a variety of languages enables humans to grow and understand the richness and diversity of the world. Humboldt claims that social interaction benefits both individuals and society alike. It leads not only to personal development, but also toward political and social harmony (Humboldt, 1836, pp. 56-57).

While Humboldt (1792/1854) claims that freedom, personal experience, and social interaction are necessary conditions for *Bildung*, he criticizes the fact that, all too often, they are not ensured. This impedes people from striving towards *Bildung* and, consequently, towards *eudaimonia*. In particular, he lists specific factors that hinder individuals from fulfilling their potential, such as religious dogmatism (p. 89), authoritarian state leadership (p. 3), and a tendency towards a superficial mindset which equates happiness with possession and pleasure (p. 2). Some of these examples once more display Humboldt's underlying idealization of the ancient Greeks. In this way, he closes the circle between his biographical background, the anthropological foundations, and the further development of his concept of *Bildung*, which pursues *eudaimonia* as its ultimate goal.

5. Conclusion

This article claims that Wilhelm von Humboldt's educational concept of *Bildung* pursues *eudaimonia* in the Aristotelian sense as its underlying goal. Based on a biographical analysis, a comparative study of Humboldt's and Aristotle's ethical foundations, and a reconstruction of Humboldt's theory of *Bildung*, I conclude the following: Essentially, the *telos teleiotion* of *Bildung* is indeed *eudaimonia*. Reaching this conclusion is challenging insofar as Humboldt's writing style is in some instances vague, ambiguous, and inconsistent. Furthermore, he only wrote a few fragments on *Bildung* exclusively, and neither outlined his argument explicitly nor systematized his ideas into a theory. Therefore, I interpret and reconstruct his line of thought based on a variety of his manuscripts and simultaneously take his biographical background into account.

The results indicate that Humboldt, who glorified the ancient Greeks, adopted the essence of Aristotle's anthropological foundation by assuming that all beings naturally have a desire for *eudaimonia*, which they can approach by fulfilling their specific potential. With this in mind, we can see that Humboldt developed Aristotle's idea further by focusing on the practical realization of the process towards *eudaimonia*, which is *Bildung*. The following figure illustrates the foundations of Humboldt's conception of *Bildung* and its interconnectedness with *eudaimonia*.

Fig. 3: Humboldt's concept of *Bildung* as a key to *eudaimonia*

What this all amounts to is that Humboldt assumed that human beings have innate vital powers (*Kraft, Energie, Trieb, Sehnsucht*) that stimulate them to fulfill their unique potential. These life forces unfold if the necessary and sufficient external conditions are met, which means that humans are free and exposed to a variety of situations through a diversity of educational content, personal experience, and social interaction. The cultivation of their faculties is guided by reason and supported by imagination and emotion. This process is called *Bildung*. In this context, humans develop both telic virtues that lead towards *eudaimonia* and autotelic virtues, as Humboldt was convinced that a virtuous life is a happy life.

To better understand the implications of these results, future studies could investigate how the foundations of Humboldt's concept of *Bildung* shaped the further development of humankind through a more holistic approach to education like, for example, the United Nations' educational concept as stated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN General Assembly, 1948)

and the Sustainable Development Goals (UN General Assembly, 2015). Another direction could be how the eudemonistic rationale of Humboldt's ideal of *Bildung* inspired other disciplines, such as the schools of thought of humanistic psychology and positive psychology. Moreover, it would be worthwhile investigating how Humboldt's conditions for *Bildung* translate into the 21st century. Consequently, one could explore how these conditions can be fostered, so that the *Bildung* of a sufficiently large number of individuals eventually evolves into the flourishing of humankind in its entirety. Other highly relevant topics that could be focalized are Humboldt's progressive notions of diversity, interdisciplinarity, and cosmopolitanism as integrated parts of his concept of *Bildung*, which could enrich today's educational and political discussion. This article provides a foundation for constructive thoughts, but the discussion on Humboldt's educational ideal of *Bildung* is nowhere near exhausted.

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